

AN ELEMENTARY OPPOSITE-PAIR OBSTRUCTION FOR EVEN REGULAR POLYGONS IN THE RATIONAL-DISTANCE PROBLEM

YUAN SI

ABSTRACT. We record a short elementary obstruction for the all-vertices rational-distance problem for even regular polygons. Let P_n be a regular n -gon of rational side length. If n is even and $n \geq 8$, then there is no point in the Euclidean plane whose distances to all vertices of P_n are rational. The proof uses only opposite vertex pairs. For a pair of opposite vertices Ru and $-Ru$, subtracting squared distances gives $R(P \cdot u) \in \mathbb{Q}$. When $n = 2m$ with $m \geq 4$, the directions $0, \pi/m, (m-1)\pi/m, 2\pi/m$ force $RP = 0$, while the unit side-length circumradius is irrational. The endpoint cases explain the exceptional nature of the square and the hexagon: the square has too few directions for this linear obstruction, whereas the unit regular hexagon has the centre as a rational-distance point. Combined with Barbara's results for the remaining cases, this isolates the square as the only remaining regular-polygon case not settled by known results and the elementary even-polygon obstruction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let $P_n(s)$ be a regular n -gon in the Euclidean plane with side length $s > 0$. We say that a point P is a *rational-distance point* for $P_n(s)$ if

$$|P - A| \in \mathbb{Q}$$

for every vertex A of $P_n(s)$. Unless explicitly stated otherwise, no interior condition is imposed. Thus every non-existence result in this note is stronger than the corresponding interior non-existence result.

If $s \in \mathbb{Q}_{>0}$, rationally rescaling the plane by $1/s$ preserves the property that all vertex distances are rational. Hence, throughout the proof, it is enough to treat the unit side-length case.

The square case $n = 4$ is the classical four-distance problem, recorded for example in Guy's problem list [6] and studied by Berry [4]. This case remains open in its usual unit-square form. The regular-polygon problem, however, is much more rigid away from the square. Barbara proved in [1] that, for a unit regular polygon, the answer is negative for $n = 5$ and for all

$$n \geq 7, \quad n \notin \{8, 12, 24\}.$$

The values 8, 12, 24 appeared as possible exceptions in that paper. Barbara later gave a complete answer to the all-vertices polygon problem apart from the square case [2]; related short notes include Bentin's work on regular polygonal distances [3]. Meskhishvili also treated the case $n = 24$ in [8, Theorem 5.1].

The purpose of the present note is not to make a priority claim for the classification. It is to isolate a self-contained opposite-pair argument which excludes all even regular polygons with $n \geq 8$ at once. The result is the following.

2020 *Mathematics Subject Classification.* 11D25, 51M04, 11R32.

Key words and phrases. Rational distance problem, regular polygon, unit polygon, opposite vertices, square four-distance problem.

University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, Canada. Email: y3si@uwaterloo.ca. ORCID: 0009-0005-1233-6972.

Theorem 1.1. *Let $n \geq 8$ be even. A regular n -gon with rational side length has no rational-distance point in the Euclidean plane.*

The proof explains the special roles of $n = 4$ and $n = 6$. The square has too few directions: opposite pairs only give two rational linear conditions. The hexagon has enough symmetry to behave differently, but its unit circumradius is rational, and the centre is a rational-distance point. For every even $n \geq 8$, the additional directions force the point to be the centre, and then the irrationality of the circumradius gives a contradiction.

2. TWO CONSEQUENCES OF NIVEN'S THEOREM

We use Niven's theorem in its standard form: if $\theta/\pi \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\sin \theta \in \mathbb{Q}$, then

$$\sin \theta \in \left\{ 0, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm 1 \right\}.$$

The corresponding cosine statement follows by applying the sine statement to $\pi/2 - \theta$.

Lemma 2.1. *For every integer $m \geq 4$,*

$$\cos \frac{\pi}{m} \notin \mathbb{Q}.$$

Proof. By Niven's theorem [7], if $\theta/\pi \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\cos \theta \in \mathbb{Q}$, then

$$\cos \theta \in \left\{ 0, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm 1 \right\}.$$

For $m \geq 4$, we have

$$0 < \frac{\pi}{m} \leq \frac{\pi}{4},$$

and hence

$$1 > \cos \frac{\pi}{m} \geq \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} > \frac{1}{2}.$$

This interval contains none of the rational values allowed by Niven's theorem. Therefore $\cos(\pi/m) \notin \mathbb{Q}$. \square

Lemma 2.2. *For every integer $n \geq 8$, the circumradius*

$$R_n = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/n)}$$

of the unit regular n -gon is irrational.

Proof. Suppose, for contradiction, that $R_n \in \mathbb{Q}$. Then

$$\sin \frac{\pi}{n} = \frac{1}{2R_n} \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since π/n is a rational multiple of π , Niven's theorem gives

$$\sin \frac{\pi}{n} \in \left\{ 0, \pm \frac{1}{2}, \pm 1 \right\}.$$

But for $n \geq 8$,

$$0 < \sin \frac{\pi}{n} \leq \sin \frac{\pi}{8} < \frac{1}{2},$$

which is impossible. Thus $R_n \notin \mathbb{Q}$. \square

3. THE OPPOSITE-PAIR OBSTRUCTION

We now prove the basic linear obstruction. It is the only geometric input.

Lemma 3.1 (Opposite-pair rationality). *Let $R > 0$, let $u \in \mathbb{R}^2$ be a unit vector, and let $P \in \mathbb{R}^2$. If*

$$|P - Ru| \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad |P + Ru| \in \mathbb{Q},$$

then

$$R(P \cdot u) \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Proof. The squared distances are rational. Subtracting them gives

$$\begin{aligned} |P - Ru|^2 - |P + Ru|^2 &= (P - Ru) \cdot (P - Ru) - (P + Ru) \cdot (P + Ru) \\ &= -4R(P \cdot u). \end{aligned}$$

Thus $R(P \cdot u) \in \mathbb{Q}$. □

Proposition 3.2. *Let $n = 2m$ with $m \geq 4$. For a unit regular n -gon, any rational-distance point would have to be the centre.*

Proof. Place the polygon with centre at the origin and with one vertex on the positive x -axis. Let

$$\theta = \frac{2\pi}{n} = \frac{\pi}{m}, \quad R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/n)}$$

be the central angle and the circumradius. The opposite-pair directions may be taken as

$$u_k = (\cos k\theta, \sin k\theta), \quad k = 0, 1, \dots, m-1.$$

Let $P = (x, y)$ be a rational-distance point and set

$$A := Rx, \quad B := Ry.$$

By Lemma 3.1,

$$q_k := R(P \cdot u_k) = A \cos(k\theta) + B \sin(k\theta) \in \mathbb{Q}$$

for every $k = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$.

First, $q_0 = A$, so

$$A \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Next,

$$q_1 = A \cos \theta + B \sin \theta \in \mathbb{Q},$$

and, since $(m-1)\theta = \pi - \theta$,

$$q_{m-1} = -A \cos \theta + B \sin \theta \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Subtracting gives

$$2A \cos \theta \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Since $A \in \mathbb{Q}$ and $\cos \theta = \cos(\pi/m)$ is irrational by Lemma 2.1, we must have

$$A = 0.$$

Adding q_1 and q_{m-1} gives

$$2B \sin \theta \in \mathbb{Q},$$

hence

$$B \sin \theta \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

Because $m \geq 4$, the direction u_2 is available, and with $A = 0$ we also have

$$q_2 = B \sin(2\theta) \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

If $B \neq 0$, then the quotient of these two rational numbers would give

$$\frac{B \sin(2\theta)}{B \sin \theta} = 2 \cos \theta \in \mathbb{Q},$$

contradicting Lemma 2.1. Therefore $B = 0$.

Thus $A = B = 0$, and since $R > 0$ this implies $x = y = 0$. Hence P is the centre. \square

Proof of Theorem 1.1. By rational scaling, assume that the side length is 1. Write $n = 2m$ with $m \geq 4$. By Proposition 3.2, any rational-distance point would have to be the centre. The distance from the centre to each vertex is the circumradius

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/n)}.$$

By Lemma 2.2, this number is irrational for $n \geq 8$. Hence the centre is not a rational-distance point, a contradiction. \square

4. THE ENDPOINT CASES $n = 4$ AND $n = 6$

The proof of Theorem 1.1 starts at $n = 8$ for structural reasons.

For $n = 4$, there are only two opposite-pair directions. After placing the square with sides parallel to the coordinate axes, Lemma 3.1 gives only

$$Rx \in \mathbb{Q}, \quad Ry \in \mathbb{Q}.$$

There is no further vertex direction available to impose an irrational linear relation. Thus the opposite-pair obstruction cannot address the square. This is precisely the classical four-distance problem.

For $n = 6$, the method fails for a different reason. Here $m = 3$ and

$$\cos \frac{\pi}{3} = \frac{1}{2}$$

is rational, so the step forcing $A = 0$ in Proposition 3.2 is no longer valid. More importantly, the unit regular hexagon has rational circumradius

$$R = \frac{1}{2 \sin(\pi/6)} = 1.$$

Therefore the centre is a rational-distance point. Thus the hexagon is a genuine positive case.

Remark 4.1. This gives a simple explanation for the different behavior of the square and the hexagon. The square is not rigid enough: it lacks extra vertex directions. The hexagon has additional directions, but its unit circumradius is rational. Every even regular polygon with $n \geq 8$ has both the extra directions and an irrational unit circumradius, and the two features together give the obstruction.

5. RELATION TO THE KNOWN CLASSIFICATION

Combining Theorem 1.1 with known results for the remaining cases gives the usual picture for rational side length regular polygons.

Corollary 5.1. *For regular polygons with rational side length, the all-vertices rational-distance problem has the following status:*

- (1) $n = 3$ and $n = 6$ have rational-distance points;
- (2) $n = 5$ and all $n \geq 7$ have no rational-distance point;
- (3) $n = 4$ is the classical square four-distance problem.

Consequently, conditional on a negative answer to the square four-distance problem, the only regular polygons with rational side length admitting a rational-distance point are the triangle and the hexagon.

Proof. The case $n = 6$ is supplied by the centre of the unit regular hexagon. The case $n = 3$ has rational-distance points; if zero distances are allowed, a vertex of a unit equilateral triangle already gives one, and non-degenerate constructions are classical, see Berry [5]. Barbara's theorem [1] excludes $n = 5$ and all $n \geq 7$ except possibly 8, 12, 24. The exceptional values 8, 12, 24 are even and at least 8, so they are covered by Theorem 1.1. Finally, $n = 4$ is exactly the unit-square four-distance problem after rational scaling. \square

Remark 5.2 (No priority claim). The preceding corollary is included to show how the elementary even-polygon obstruction fits into the standard classification. It should not be read as a claim that the full classification is new here. In particular, Barbara's later note [2] gives the complete all-vertices polygon answer apart from the square case. The contribution of the present note is the short self-contained proof of the even cases $n \geq 8$ and the accompanying explanation of why the square and the hexagon are exceptional endpoints.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Barbara, *Points at rational distance from the vertices of a unit polygon*, Bull. Iranian Math. Soc. **35** (2009), no. 2, 209–215; arXiv:0912.2981.
- [2] R. Barbara, *97.11 The rational distance problem for polygons*, Math. Gaz. **97** (2013), no. 538, 144–149. DOI: 10.1017/S0025557200005581.
- [3] J. Bentin, *81.32 Regular polygonal distances*, Math. Gaz. **81** (1997), no. 491, 277–279. DOI: 10.2307/3619212.
- [4] T. G. Berry, *Points at rational distance from the corners of a unit square*, Ann. Scuola Norm. Sup. Pisa Cl. Sci. (4) **17** (1990), no. 4, 505–529.
- [5] T. G. Berry, *Points at rational distance from the vertices of a triangle*, Acta Arith. **62** (1992), no. 4, 391–398. DOI: 10.4064/aa-62-4-391-398.
- [6] R. K. Guy, *Unsolved Problems in Number Theory*, 3rd ed., Springer, New York, 2004.
- [7] I. Niven, *Irrational Numbers*, Carus Mathematical Monographs, no. 11, Mathematical Association of America, 1956.
- [8] M. Meskhishvili, *Cyclic averages of regular polygons and Platonic solids*, Commun. Math. Appl. **11** (2020), no. 3, 335–355; arXiv:2010.12340. DOI: 10.26713/cma.v11i3.1420.